

Paper 3

Learning Analytics: The Emergence of Big Data and Analytics into Learning, Education, And Research—An Overview

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Abstract

Big Data is an emerging technology which is dedicated to managing large amounts of data and also for complex data. Big Data is the need of hours for managing growing information in different sectors. Big Data and the procedure become common in managing different types of data of various fields as well and it is called Data Analytics. Data Analytics is important in various educational activities as well and that leads learning analytics as an important area of practice. The application of Big Data and Analytics in diverse areas developed many other fields such as Business Analytics, Healthcare Analytics, Marketing Analytics, and most emerging Learning Analytics as well. The applications of Big Data and Analytics is important in normal teaching learning activities, online and virtual education and training programs, distance learning and open education systems. Further in managing educational systems, management and organization also Big Data plays an important role in the entire education, training, and research sectors. Big Data Analytics is emerging with different services and facilities to the academic institutions and community. Data Science and its growth as a field leading entire educational systems and it helps in efficient, smarter, quick, and advanced educational organization and management. This paper discussed briefly on Big Data, Data Analytics with reference to the applications to Education, Training, and Research.

Keywords: Big Data, Data Analytics, Data Science, Educational Management, Learning Analytics, Educational Analytics

Introduction

Learning Analytics is one of the emerging technologies within the Information Technology domain with importance in education, teaching, training, research, etc. Learning Analytics is the combination of Analytics and Learning/Education Segment. It is the way, procedure and method of measuring, collecting, analyzing, reporting of the data of the learners and their context. Learning Analytics is helpful in a healthy and optimize the learning environment. There was tremendous growth of online and digital education since the 1990s specifically in

the higher education domain therefore various data generated and captured at the various time may be recorded using Learning Analytics effectively [1], [15]. The perception of the users regarding online tools, their uses, searching pattern, and content in relation to education may be seen using Learning Analytics. Here Learning Management System, Navigation pattern, time on task, social networks, information flow, MOOCs can be used to analyze and to get further decision. There are many capabilities of Learning Analytics and some of them are given below in Fig: 1.

Fig: 1-Showing core capabilities of Learning Analytics

Big Data become an important name in Data Management, however another allied concept and tool called Data Analytics, Data Science also played a leading role in this segment [8], [9], [19]. Learning analytics results in an effective teaching learning process, effective educational management and development, proper and balanced digitalization, and so on.

Objective

The present paper entitled ‘Learning Analytics the Emergence of Big Data and Analytics into Learning, Education, and Research—*An Overview*’ is research based and particularly deals with the following aim and objective—

- To learn about the basics of Learning Analytics including features and characteristics in a concise manner.

- To know about the basics of Big Data and Analytics including foundational aspects and applications in other subjects.
- To learn about the applications of Big Data and Analytics in the field of Education, training, and research.
- To learn about the contemporary scenario of Big Data Applications in Education, teaching, and research.
- To know about the issues and challenges of Big Data Applications in educational systems and management.
- To view Learning Analytics in the light of Big Data, Data Science, and allied systems.

Learning Analytics: An Overview

Learning Analytics is particularly the tool and way in the collection, analysis of various kinds of data related to the learners including their perception, environments, etc. which helps in understanding and improving healthy and advanced learning outcomes [5], [6], [21]. There is a basic difference in respect of the application of Big Data in Education and Learning Analytics. The first one is the full application of Big Data into Education, teaching, and research whereas the second one is particularly on collecting quantitative data of the learners from different stakeholders like Governments, Universities, Educational Agencies and Ministries, Online Course Platforms, Social Media, and so on. Learning Analytics is very particular on how learners learn and their perception and mentality in a broader sense. Today there are different platforms to collect the data but a limited number of proper ways in gathering such data in neat, organized, and proper format; and in this regard Learning Analytics is worthy and emerging. The analysis is very important to reach a particular decision; and in this context Learning analytics and educational data mining are the tools to transform this data into knowledge and lead, in the end, to improved education [2], [18], [27]. One of LaCroix in respect of Learning Analytics is very worthy i.e. “Having an analytics program in place is not a magical solution to educational challenges, however,” There are many ways and reasons in adopting Learning Analytics internationally and these important are—

- To measure the main or key indicators of student’s activities and performance with proper data analysis.
- To support student development in a holistic manner.
- To understand, plan and executive in respect of improving the effectiveness of teaching and learning practices.
- To guide and inform institutional decisions and strategies properly and effectively.

Fig: 2-The foundations and stakeholders of Learning Analytics

Learning Analytics, therefore, is a healthy practice of analysis with strong communication between the analyst and analyst in order to reach the actual goal. Listening to the needs of teachers and students, and other stakeholders are important in Learning Analytics for proper data-driven decision making as depicted in Fig: 2.

Big Data: Basics

Big Data is increasing day by day due to information proliferation. Data basically generates in different formats, mediums, and ways; and Big Data is a proper technique to manage a large amount of complex data. Therefore, it is also called as Big Data Management and it is worthy to mention that here Analytics play a leading role with applications in diverse areas and sectors. Therefore, Big Data application results in different sectors such as i.e., Business Analytics (which may be considered as Big Data into Management, Business and Corporate), Health Analytics (This is the application in healthcare, medical areas), Retail Analytics (The application of Big Data in retail sectors results in this), etc. refer Fig: 3 for details. As far as other areas are concerned Big Data applications are remarkable like in Transportation, Governance, Education, Business, Manufacturing, etc. All we know that Information Technology is an important tool for the purpose of information solutions and important in the modernization of society at a large and thus it is considered as important in proper Social Informatics practice [3], [20].

Data is important for everything such as Healthcare sector, Government, Business and Industries, Agriculture and horticulture, Management, Education and Training, etc. and for proper management of such data i.e., managing large amounts and complex data management Big Data Management is powered by different analytical tools and thus it is also known as Data Analytics [18], [28]. The applications of Analytics in different areas leads to various other areas as mentioned before—

- Business Analytics (results of merging & combining Big Data/ Analytics in Business & Industries).
- Healthcare Analytics (results of merging & combining the Big Data/ Analytics in Healthcare and Medical Systems).
- Marketing/Retail Analytics (It is Big Data/ Analytics in Marketing and Retail merger).
- Government Analytics (results of merging & combining of Big Data/ Analytics in Government Analytics) [10], [12], [16].
- Learning Analytics (Big Data/ Analytics in Education, Teaching, and Learning results in this).

Fig: 3-General applications of Big Data Applications in diverse areas

Big Data in Education, Training, and HR

Education is an important sector, and we all are dependent on education and there are huge uses of Big Data/Analytics in this sector such as education, training, research, etc. Various student related data or student needy data viz. on programs, courses/ papers, universities, enrollment year, student ID, exam results and grades Analytics is worthy. Therefore, Analytics is helpful in managed and can be beneficial for organizations and institutions. Further as far as analyzing the behaviors of the student is concerned Big Data/ Analytics can be considered as valuable. As far as monitoring, exam preparation, and progress, feedback analysis is concerned Big Data considered worthy [7], [17], [19]. The recent developments of online mode, digital mode of learning is fortunate enough with Big Data/ Analytics applications potentiality. Big Data in educational activities required in some activities like student dropout, predictive analytics, carrier insights, etc.

Learning Analytics Very Particular Applications

As far as very particular applications of Learning Analytics are concerned it empowers many benefits and among these few important are—

In Enhancing Student Results

The student's results are considered as important in a proper education system and as far as Learning Analytics is concerned it is valuable in analyzing many student's examination data based on their obtained marks, grades. Learning Analytics also helps in gathering proper data in projects, assignments, dissertations, which questions most of the students answered, sources they choose, question they skip and most attend, etc [7], [25]. Therefore, analyzing these data trails will help educators and educational institutions to understand the behavior as well as the performance of the concerned students. The real time data analysis is possible using their feedback.

In Proper and Improved Grading

Learning Analytics is helpful in helping proper and improved grading in many ways. The educators help in tracking the performance of the students. The statistical analysis of individual grades is finally helpful in better and proper educational planning in terms of student's further development and such techniques also helpful in gaining the areas where the student has excelled. A right career path is many ways possible to find out using Learning Analytics techniques by proper analysis. There are many tools being used such as Socrative, Nearpod and Classroom Monitor for analyzing their students. Therefore, it not only helps in knowing the feedback but also the way to enhance their students' performances and to give the best solutions.

In Gaining Attention

As far as gaining attention is concerned Learning Analytics is considered as important and valuable. In educational systems Learning Analytics is applicable in gaining attendance among the students particularly the analysis of the student's trend in a particular class, to a particular subject, to a particular teacher, etc. Many students are absent minded during the classes and even in such cases also Learning Analytics is fruitful. Here various biometric, smart-watches, similar tools are being used [4], [13], [26].

In Proper Designing of Curriculum and Programs

Learning Analytics is very fruitful in preparing proper designing of the curriculum and programs. The educators and educational administrators are able to know the grades of the students and their status of education and as a result based on that future curriculum and

programs. Based on the even need of the students online, blended educational systems can be introduced [14], [22]. Therefore, here Big Data and Analytics are useful properly.

In Reducing number of Dropouts

Even according to the expert Learning Analytics also fruitful in finding the number of dropouts by proper analysis of the data. Here performing predictive analysis is useful to understand how students might perform in the near future. This analysis is helpful in knowing the performance of students throughout the year, and the continuous data analysis is helpful in reducing the number of dropouts [11], [23], [24]. With proper Learning Analytics authorities to execute a scenario of a student, batch and group, and analysis, this is ultimately helping teachers to guide their students and proper suggestion.

Conclusion

Therefore, it is important that Learning Analytics is one of the emerging technologies within the Information Technology domain with importance in education. Digital education and system changed the entire arena of modern education. The study shows that since the 1990s specifically in the higher education domain various data generated and captured at various times, and all such may be recorded using Learning Analytics effectively. Though there are certain issues in implementing Analytics into the Education segment and among these important are technological infrastructure, proper initiatives, government support, digital divide, lack of awareness, etc. In developing countries, there are certain issues in implanting Learning Analytics, and such need to overcome by proper initiative.

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